

EXPLORING FPGA ACCELERATION FOR CMS RECONSTRUCTION USING ALPAKA

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ABSTRACT

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This report details the porting and optimization of the CLUE clustering algorithm for the CMS experiment onto an Altera Agilex 7 FPGA. The primary goal was to explore the feasibility of using a SYCL-based High-Level Synthesis workflow within the alpaka performance portability framework to accelerate high-energy physics workloads on spatial architectures. Through an iterative process of analyzing compiler reports and refactoring code, the CLUE kernels were optimized to mitigate memory and data dependencies. The final design is synthesized to operate at 480 MHz, with most critical loops achieving a high-throughput Initiation Interval (II) of 1. Static analysis reveals the implementation is memory-centric, consuming 30% of the FPGA's on-chip RAM while making minimal use of logic and DSP resources. Although a hardware fault with the accelerator card precluded final performance validation on physical hardware, the synthesis and simulation results establish a robust and highly-optimized baseline, demonstrating the viability of this approach for future heterogeneous computing at CMS.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The unprecedented data volumes from the CERN Large Hadron Collider (LHC) and its upcoming High-Luminosity (HL-LHC) upgrade present a significant computational challenge for the Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) experiment. To meet the tight, millisecond-level execution time budget for event reconstruction, CMS has actively explored heterogeneous computing platforms. This effort began with the adoption of NVIDIA GPUs in 2017, leading to a substantial increase in event processing throughput.

However, the proliferation of different hardware architectures, including GPUs from various vendors (NVIDIA, AMD, Intel) and other accelerators like FPGAs, introduced a new challenge: code portability. Developing and maintaining separate codebases for each architecture duplicates effort and introduces bugs. To address this, CMS has adopted `alpaka`, a C++ template library that enables performance portability, allowing a single source code to run on multiple accelerators without extensive rewrites.

This project continues that effort by exploring the integration of the Intel oneAPI toolchain for FPGA programming into the `alpaka` framework. By porting the CLUE clustering algorithm to an FPGA, we aim to investigate the feasibility and performance of this approach, contributing to CMS's long-term heterogeneous computing strategy. Traditionally, FPGAs are programmed using a Hardware Description Language (HDL) like Verilog or VHDL. However, a recent trend is to use High-Level Synthesis (HLS), which allows developers to use higher-level languages like C++. This approach can significantly reduce design time and increase portability, which aligns perfectly with the goals of this project. ¹

2 BACKGROUND: FPGAs AND SYCL

2.1 What is an FPGA?

Unlike conventional CPUs and GPUs, which have a fixed Instruction Set Architecture (ISA), Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) are spatial architectures. This means that a program is mapped directly onto a configurable hardware fabric, creating a physical dataflow pipeline. Different parts of the program execute on different regions of the device simultaneously, enabling extreme parallelism and compelling energy efficiency. While an application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) generally offers higher performance, its immutable design requires significant time and financial investment. FPGAs provide a more flexible and cost-effective alternative, as they can be reprogrammed for new applications.

As can be seen in Figure 1, an FPGA consists of a grid of programmable logic blocks, often called Adaptive Logic Modules (ALMs), alongside specialized blocks for Digital Signal Processing (DSP) and Random Access Memory (RAM). These components are connected via configurable routing interconnects.

A simplified ALM contains a lookup table (LUT), which can implement any arbitrary Boolean logic, and a register, which is the most basic storage element that synchronizes data to a clock signal. DSP blocks are hardwired to perform arithmetic operations like multiplication and addition efficiently, while RAM blocks provide dense, on-chip data storage.

¹The source code for this project is publicly available at: <https://github.com/MohamadKhaledCharaf/CLUE-SYCL>

(a) High-level architectural view showing the grid of programmable blocks.

(b) Simplified view of a Register

Figure 1: Views of an FPGA’s internal structure.[3]

2.2 Why FPGAs at CMS?

The CMS experiment constantly seeks new ways to accelerate its data processing. This project evaluates FPGAs as a compelling choice for accelerating specific, computationally intensive algorithms within the High Level Trigger (HLT) reconstruction software. While the HLT processes a data rate that is significantly reduced by the initial trigger stages, it must execute complex algorithms within a latency budget on the order of seconds. The inherent parallelism of FPGAs allows them to perform these demanding tasks with high throughput and predictable latency, making them an ideal solution for offloading specific workloads from the HLT’s CPU farm to improve the overall system efficiency.

2.3 What is SYCL?

SYCL is an open-standard, C++-based programming model that enables code to be written once and deployed across various hardware accelerators, including CPUs, GPUs, and FPGAs. It provides an abstraction layer that allows developers to write platform-agnostic code, which is then compiled for a specific target architecture. The Intel oneAPI DPC++ compiler, an implementation of the SYCL standard, provides specific extensions and features for FPGA development.

Figure 2: Block diagram of the BittWare IA-840f board featuring the Intel Agilex 7 AGF027 FPGA. [1]

2.4 The Target FPGA: Altera Agilex 7

At the heart of the BittWare IA-840f (see Figure 2) is the Intel® Agilex™ 7 AGF027 FPGA. According to the official device overview [2], this FPGA provides a rich set of programmable resources, including 2,696K Logic Elements (LEs), 3,840 high-performance 18x19 DSP blocks, and 51.3 Mb of embedded M20K RAM. In addition, the device features numerous hardened intellectual property (IP) blocks to support high-speed interfaces, providing native support for a PCIe Gen4 ×16 interface.

Complementing the on-chip resources, the IA-840f board features a high-performance memory subsystem configured according to the Board Support Package (BSP). The system utilizes two 512-bit wide DDR4 channels that support memory interleaving with a 4 kB stride to maximize throughput. According to the optimization report, the theoretical maximum bandwidth the BSP can deliver is 42.7 GB/s. However, the report notes that a more realistic peak bandwidth is approximately 90% of this value (around 38.4 GB/s) due to overhead from the interconnect and memory controller. The BSP further characterizes the performance with a maximum read bandwidth of 42.7 GB/s and a write bandwidth of 21.6 GB/s.

Furthermore, a separate host-shared memory region accessible over the PCIe interface delivers up to 30 GB/s, enabling efficient CPU–FPGA communication.

2.5 Key FPGA Concepts

2.5.1 Pipelining and Maximum Frequency (f_{MAX})

In a digital circuit, the maximum clock frequency (f_{MAX}) is limited by the propagation delay of signals through combinational logic between two consecutive registers. The longest path, known as the **critical path**, determines the speed of the entire circuit. **Pipelining** is a technique used to increase f_{MAX} by inserting additional registers into the critical path. This breaks a long combinational path into shorter, faster stages, allowing the circuit to run at a higher clock frequency.

2.5.2 Datapath and Occupancy

A **datapath** is the network of registers and logic that performs computations. The **occupancy** of a datapath refers to the proportion of its pipeline stages that contain valid data at any given time. Unoccupied stages, known as **bubbles**, are analogous to no-operation (no-op) instructions for a CPU and reduce throughput.

While deeper pipelining increases f_{MAX} and peak throughput as illustrated by the example in Figure 3, it also increases latency, as more clock cycles are required to fill the pipeline initially. This trade-off is crucial: for applications processing large, continuous streams of data, the initial latency is easily amortized, and the gains in throughput are significant.

Figure 3: An example of a datapath where a pipeline register is inserted to break a long combinational logic path into two shorter stages, enabling a higher f_{MAX} [3]

2.5.3 Scheduling

Scheduling is the process of assigning each operation in an FPGA design to a specific clock cycle. The goal is to create a deeply pipelined architecture that allows multiple operations to execute concurrently, maximizing throughput.

Dynamic Scheduling The Intel DPC++ Compiler creates a dynamically scheduled, pipelined datapath. In this model, an operation does not pass data to the next stage until the successor signals it is ready. This is achieved using handshaking control logic with ‘valid’ and ‘stall’ signals. This mechanism is essential for handling variable-latency operations (e.g., memory access) without creating pipeline bubbles.

Clustering the Datapath (Figure 4) To reduce the area overhead from handshaking logic, the compiler groups fixed-latency operations into **clusters**. This approach confines handshaking interfaces to the cluster boundaries, simplifying the control logic.

Cluster Types The compiler supports two cluster types:

- **Stall-Enable Cluster (SEC):** Propagates the ‘stall’ signal to all internal stages in parallel. It is area-efficient but can only remove leading bubbles from the pipeline.
- **Stall-Free Cluster (SFC):** Includes an exit FIFO that allows the cluster to continue processing even when stalled downstream. It is more effective at removing bubbles but requires more area.

Figure 4: Illustration of datapath clustering. Fixed-latency operations are grouped, and handshaking logic is only required between clusters and variable-latency units.[3]

2.5.4 Leveraging Parallelism

FPGAs achieve high performance by exploiting parallelism on a massive scale. Instead of executing a sequence of instructions like a CPU, FPGAs create a physical circuit customized for the algorithm. This enables two primary forms of parallelism: pipelining (temporal parallelism) and vectorization (spatial parallelism).

Pipelining As discussed previously, pipelining breaks a computation into a series of smaller stages. The key to parallelism is that new data can enter the first stage of the pipeline on every clock cycle, even before the first piece of data has finished its entire journey. As illustrated in Figure 5, this approach keeps all stages of the hardware datapath occupied simultaneously, maximizing occupancy and throughput. The compiler applies this principle to loops, aiming for an **Initiation Interval (II)** of 1, where a new loop iteration can begin every single clock cycle.

Figure 5: Illustration of a pipelined datapath. New data (t0, t1, t2...) enters the pipeline on subsequent clock cycles, keeping the hardware fully occupied.[3]

Vectorization To further increase throughput, the compiler can vectorize the hardware. As shown in Figure 6, vectorization creates multiple identical copies of the entire pipelined datapath. These parallel pipelines can then process multiple data items simultaneously. For example, three pipelines can process three data items in the time it takes one pipeline to process one, effectively tripling the throughput. This powerful technique comes at the direct cost of a proportional increase in FPGA resource usage, as the hardware logic is physically duplicated on the chip.

Figure 6: Illustration of a vectorized datapath. The pipeline is duplicated to process multiple data items in parallel, multiplying throughput at the cost of additional FPGA area.[3]

3 THE CLUE ALGORITHM

3.1 What is CLUE?

CLUE (CLUstering of Energy) is a fast, fully parallelizable density-based clustering algorithm developed for the high-occupancy environments of the CMS High Granularity Calorimeter (HGCAL) [6]. Inspired by the CFSFDP algorithm [5], CLUE is optimized for scenarios where the number of clusters is much larger than the average number of points per cluster. Its core feature is a fixed-grid spatial index for efficient neighborhood queries, which enables linear scalability. The algorithm is decomposed into several highly parallelizable kernels, making it well-suited for heterogeneous architectures like FPGAs and GPUs.

3.2 The Different Kernels of CLUE

The CLUE algorithm is decomposed into a sequence of four main kernels.

3.2.1 Spatial Indexing and Histogram Creation

The first kernel, `compute_histogram`, spatially indexes the input points (calorimeter hits shown in Figure 7) to accelerate neighborhood searches. It partitions the 2D coordinate space into a grid of tiles and stores the points belonging to each tile in a coalesced data structure. The global tile index for a point is calculated as:

$$\text{tile}_{\text{global}} = \text{tile}_{\text{row}} \times N_{\text{cols}} + \text{tile}_{\text{col}}$$

This indexing allows for constant-time ($O(1)$) neighborhood lookups in subsequent kernels.

Figure 7: Initial distribution of input points (hits) in the 2D space before clustering. [7]

3.2.2 Local Density (ρ) Calculation

The second kernel, `kernel_calculate_density`, computes the local density ρ_i for each point i as illustrated in Figure 8:

$$\rho_i = \sum_{j: d_{ij} < d_c} \chi(d_{ij}) w_j,$$

where the sum is over all neighboring points j within a cut-off distance d_c , w_j is the weight (energy) of point j , and χ is a convolution kernel. The spatial index built in the previous step is used to efficiently query for neighbors, restricting the search to a small set of adjacent tiles.

3.2.3 Nearest Higher (δ) Calculation

The third kernel calculates δ_i , the distance to the nearest point with a higher density. For each point i , the kernel searches for a point j such that $\rho_j > \rho_i$ and the Euclidean distance d_{ij} is minimized. This search is performed within a wider search window. The result of this step is a nearest-higher index for each point, forming a directed acyclic graph (DAG) where each point "points" to its nearest higher-density neighbor, as illustrated in Figure 9. Points with no higher-density neighbor are potential cluster seeds.

Figure 8: Visualization of local density (ρ). Warmer colors indicate points with higher density. [7]

Figure 9: Arrows indicating the nearest higher-density neighbor for each point, forming a directed graph. [7]

3.2.4 Seed Identification and Cluster Expansion

Figures 10 and 11 show the final stages of the CLUE algorithm. The kernels, `kernel_find_clusters` and `kernel_assign_clusters`, identify seeds and form the final clusters.

- **Seed and Outlier Identification (Figure 10):** A point is promoted to a **seed** if its local density ρ is above a threshold ρ_c and its nearest-higher distance δ is above a threshold d_m . Points with a high δ but low ρ are marked as **outliers**. All other points are **followers**.
- **Cluster Expansion (Figure 11):** For each seed, a cluster ID is assigned. This ID is then propagated to all of its followers by traversing the DAG created in the previous step. This process effectively assigns all points in a seed's "watershed" to the same cluster.

Figure 10: Cluster seeds (large circles) and outliers identified based on ρ and δ thresholds.[7]

Figure 11: Final clusters after propagating seed IDs to all follower points.[7]

4 METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 FPGA Development Workflow and Device Selection

Developing for FPGAs involves a multi-stage workflow that balances compilation speed with functional accuracy. To manage this, the Intel oneAPI toolkit provides three distinct execution modes: emulation, simulation, and physical hardware. Our implementation uses SYCL device selectors within preprocessor directives to easily switch between these targets, as shown in the code below.

```

#if FPGA_SIMULATOR
    auto selector = sycl::ext::intel::fpga_simulator_selector_v;
#elif FPGA_HARDWARE
    auto selector = sycl::ext::intel::fpga_selector_v;
#else // #if FPGA_EMULATOR
    auto selector = sycl::ext::intel::fpga_emulator_selector_v;
#endif
sycl::queue q{selector};

```

A **SYCL device selector** is an object that instructs the runtime to choose a specific type of device from all those available on the system. The three modes used in this project that can be seen on Figure 12 serve distinct purposes:

Emulation Mode Selected with `fpga_emulator_selector_v`, this mode compiles the SYCL kernel for the host CPU. Compilation is very fast (seconds to minutes), allowing for rapid functional verification and standard C++ debugging. It is used to ensure the algorithm’s logic is correct before beginning the much slower hardware synthesis process.

Simulation Mode Selected with `fpga_simulator_selector_v`, this mode first compiles the SYCL code into hardware description language (RTL) and then simulates its execution on the CPU. It is cycle-accurate, providing a detailed preview of how the logic will behave on the actual FPGA. This step is crucial for debugging hardware-specific issues and analyzing the pipeline’s performance without waiting for a full hardware build.

Hardware Mode Selected with `fpga_selector_v`, this is the final stage. The code is fully synthesized, placed, and routed to generate a bitstream that is programmed onto the physical FPGA fabric. This process can take several hours but is necessary for measuring real-world performance and deploying the accelerator.

Figure 12: FPGA Development Workflow [4]

By defining a compile-time macro (e.g., passing `-DFPGA_HARDWARE` to the compiler), we can control which selector is used and, therefore, which stage of the development workflow is targeted.

4.2 Choosing the Right Parallelism Model

A crucial decision in targeting an FPGA is choosing the right parallelism model to express the algorithm. While FPGAs excel at **pipeline parallelism**, where a single, deep execution pipeline is continuously fed with new data, SYCL provides two primary methods to generate this work: **`parallel_for` (ND-range) kernels** and **loops within single_task kernels**.

The **`parallel_for`** model, inherited from GPUs, is ideal for algorithms that can be decomposed into many **independent work-items** that require little or no communication. In this model, the FPGA pipeline is very efficiently filled by launching a new work-item every clock cycle.

However, many algorithms, including key parts of CLUE, are not easily broken down into independent tasks. They often contain **data dependencies**, where one step of the computation depends on the result of the previous one (a "loop-carried dependency"). While this pattern can be challenging for vectorized architectures like GPUs, the spatial pipeline of an FPGA handles it very efficiently.

For this reason, our implementation primarily uses **single_task kernels containing a main processing loop**, as recommended in the DPC++ documentation [4]. This approach naturally maps the algorithm's sequential dependencies onto the hardware pipeline, where the result from an earlier stage can be efficiently forwarded to a later stage for a subsequent loop iteration. This makes it a powerful and natural fit for the accumulator patterns and sequential graph traversals found in the CLUE algorithm.

4.3 Task Graph of the CLUE Implementation

The high-level task graph for the FPGA-accelerated CLUE implementation is as follows:

1. **Host-to-Device Data Transfer:** Copy input hit data from CPU host memory to the FPGA's on-board DDR4 memory.
2. **Kernel 1 - Spatial Indexing:** A `single_task` kernel builds the fixed-grid spatial index.
3. **Kernel 2 - Density Calculation:** A `single_task` kernel iterates through all hits to compute the ρ values.
4. **Kernel 3 - Separation Calculation:** A `single_task` kernel iterates through all hits to compute the δ values.
5. **Kernel 4 - Seed Finding & Assignment:** One or more `single_task` kernels identify cluster seeds and propagate cluster IDs.
6. **Device-to-Host Data Transfer:** Copy the final cluster results from the FPGA back to the host.

4.4 Memory Management and Data Transfer with SYCL USM

For this project, we managed memory on the Intel FPGA using SYCL's Unified Shared Memory (USM) model. USM provides a pointer-based interface that simplifies memory management compared to the traditional buffer-accessor model. Specifically, we chose the **explicit device allocation** approach using `sycl::malloc_device` because it offers the most granular control over data placement and movement, which is critical for optimizing performance on a discrete accelerator like an FPGA.

This explicit control is implemented through a set of helper functions that handle the entire lifecycle of device data: allocation, host-to-device transfer, on-device initialization, device-to-host transfer, and deallocation.

1. Device Memory Allocation (`init_device`) Before any computation, we reserve memory directly on the FPGA's high-bandwidth DDR4 memory using `sycl::malloc_device`. This function allocates a specified number of bytes on the accelerator and returns a USM pointer that is only accessible from device code (i.e., within a SYCL kernel). By pre-allocating a large buffer (`reserve = 1000000`), we create a persistent workspace for the largest expected dataset.

An example of this operation is shown below:

```
d_points.x = sycl::malloc_device<float>(reserve, q);
```

Here, `sycl::malloc_device<float>` allocates memory for `reserve` floating-point numbers. The `sycl::queue q` argument is essential as it provides the context, telling the SYCL runtime which specific accelerator the memory should be allocated on.

2. Host-to-Device Data Transfer (`copy_todevice`) With memory allocated on the device, we explicitly copy the input data from the host CPU to the FPGA. This is accomplished using `h.memcpy` within a command group submitted to the SYCL queue. Each `memcpy` is an asynchronous operation, and submitting each transfer in a separate command group, as shown in the code, creates a simple and clear sequence of data transfers.

The submission of a copy command follows this structure:

```
q.submit([&](sycl::handler &h) {
    h.memcpy(d_points.x, points_.p_x, sizeof(float) * points_.n);
});
```

The call to `q.submit` enqueues a new task. The `sycl::handler h` object is used to build the command for that task in this case, an `h.memcpy` from the host source (`points_.p_x`) to the device destination (`d_points.x`).

3. On-Device Buffer Initialization (`clear_internal_buffers`) Between processing different events, it is crucial to reset the state of all intermediate and output buffers. We use `q.memset` to efficiently set all bytes in these device-side buffers to zero. This is a fast, on-device operation that ensures a clean state before the CLUE kernels are launched.

This operation is a convenient shortcut on the queue object:

```
q.memset(d_points.rho, 0x00, sizeof(float) * points_.n);
```

The command instructs the device associated with queue `q` to set the memory region pointed to by `d_points.rho` to zero. This operation is executed by the FPGA's memory controller, avoiding any data transfer over the PCIe bus.

4. Device-to-Host Data Transfer (`copy_tohost`) After the CLUE kernels have finished executing, the results must be copied back to the host for analysis. This is done using explicit `h.memcpy` operations from the device USM pointers to the host's data structures.

The code is structurally identical to the host-to-device copy, but with the arguments reversed:

```
q.submit([&](sycl::handler &h) {
    h.memcpy(points_.rho.data(), d_points.rho, sizeof(float) * points_.n);
});
```

Here, the destination is the host memory location (`points_.rho.data()`) and the source is the device pointer (`d_points.rho`).

5. Memory Deallocation (`free_device`) Finally, once all processing is complete, the memory allocated on the FPGA is explicitly released using `sycl::free`. This is a critical step to prevent memory leaks on the device and return the accelerator’s resources to the system. This meticulous management of memory ensures that the application is both robust and performant.

The deallocation requires the original pointer and the queue for context:

```
sycl::free(d_points.x, q);
```

The pointer `d_points.x` identifies the memory to be released. The queue `q` is again necessary to tell the SYCL runtime which device’s memory manager is responsible for this pointer and must perform the deallocation.

4.5 Challenges Encountered

Porting the CLUE algorithm to an FPGA using SYCL presented several challenges:

- **Report-driven Optimization:** Achieving an efficient spatial pipeline is highly dependent on the DPC++ compiler. A significant part of the work involved analyzing compiler reports to identify and mitigate performance bottlenecks, such as loops with a high initiation interval (II), which directly impacts throughput.
- **Data Dependencies:** While FPGAs handle pipeline dependencies well, a naive implementation can still lead to stalls. Kernels had to be carefully structured to minimize data hazards and maximize datapath occupancy.
- **Resource Utilization:** A critical aspect of FPGA design is managing hardware resources. Designs that overutilize any single resource type (e.g., ALMs, DSPs, or RAM) exceeding 90% can be difficult for the compiler to place and route, which often degrades the final operating frequency (f_{MAX}). However, given the substantial capacity of the target Agilex 7 FPGA, this did not prove to be a significant constraint for implementing the CLUE algorithm. The kernels fit comfortably within the available resources, leaving significant capacity to spare.

5 Kernel Optimization and Performance Tuning

Achieving high throughput on an FPGA requires creating a deeply pipelined hardware design where the main processing loops can initiate a new iteration every clock cycle. This ideal state is known as an **Initiation Interval (II)** of 1. The initial implementation of the CLUE kernels, while functionally correct, suffered from high II values due to various data and memory dependencies identified in the Intel DPC++ Loop Analysis report. This section details the step-by-step optimizations applied to each kernel to reduce their II and improve overall performance.

A crucial general optimization was the consistent use of compiler hints. The attribute `[[intel::kernel_args_restrict]]` was applied to kernel definitions to inform the compiler that pointer arguments do not alias (overlap in memory). This resolves compiler conservatism and prevents it from serializing memory accesses unnecessarily. Furthermore, explicitly casting USM pointers to `sycl::ext::intel::device_ptr` within the kernel body was vital. This tells the compiler that the data resides exclusively on the device, eliminating ambiguity and preventing the generation of costly, stall-prone logic to handle potential host-side access.

5.1 Optimizing `compute_histogram`: On-Chip Memory and Caching

The `compute_histogram` kernel's primary bottleneck was a severe loop-carried memory dependency. The loop iterates through points and increments a counter for the corresponding tile. Initially, these counters resided in off-chip DDR4 memory.

- Problem:** The read-modify-write operation on an off-chip memory counter created a long-latency Read-After-Write (RAW) hazard. Each loop iteration had to wait for the previous iteration's memory write to complete before it could read the updated counter value. This resulted in an extremely high II, reported as 1157 when compiled with a Board Support Package (BSP) that models realistic memory latencies.
- Solution 1 (On-Chip Memory):** The first and most impactful optimization was to move the tile-size counters from off-chip DDR4 to on-chip Block RAM (BRAM). This was achieved by declaring a local array, `int tileSizes[NLAYERS][T::nTiles];`, within the `single_task` kernel. This dramatically reduced the memory access latency, dropping the loop II from over 1000 to just 2.

Figure 13: Loop Carried Dependency with $II=2$

- Remaining Bottleneck ($II=2$):** Although much improved, the II remained at 2. The Loop Analysis report confirmed that the read-modify-write cycle to the on-chip memory still constituted a loop-carried dependency that took more than a single clock cycle to resolve as can be seen in Figure 13.
- Solution 2 (On-Chip Caching):** To achieve the ideal II of 1, the "On-chip Memory Cache Technique" described in the Intel FPGA handbook is necessary [3]. This technique breaks the dependency by creating a small, register-based cache for recently accessed counter values. A read-modify-write operation on a register can complete in a single cycle. By servicing memory requests from this cache, the dependency chain is broken. While a manual attempt was made using the `[[intel::ivdep]]` attribute to assert no dependency, the most robust solution involves using Intel's provided caching classes, which is a clear path for future work.

5.2 Optimizing `CalculateDensity` and `CalculateDistanceToHigher`: Refactoring Data Dependencies

The density and distance calculation kernels both feature a triply nested loop structure to iterate over neighboring points. The initial implementation suffered from a classic loop-carried data dependency that serialized the outer loops.

- **Problem:** An accumulator variable (e.g., `rhoi` in `CalculateDensity`) was updated in the innermost loop. Because each iteration of an outer loop depended on the final accumulated value from all iterations of its inner loops, the compiler could not pipeline them. The outer loop had to stall until the entire nested structure below it completed, leading to poor hardware utilization and high latency.
- **Solution (Dependency Refactoring):** The solution was to decouple the computations by introducing local accumulator variables at each loop level. For example, in `CalculateDensity`, variables `rho2` and `rho1` were introduced for the inner and middle loops, respectively. The innermost loop accumulates into `rho2`, which is then added to `rho1` at the end of the middle loop. Finally, `rho1` is added to the main accumulator `rhoi` at the end of the outer loop. This refactoring breaks the dependency chain, allowing the compiler to pipeline all three nested loops with an II of 1. The attribute `[[intel::initiation_interval(1)]]` was added to explicitly guide the compiler towards this goal.

The optimized code structure for `CalculateDensity` is shown below:

```

1   for(int i = 0 ; i < numberOfPoints ; ++i){
2       float rhoi = 0.;
3       // ... setup for point i ...
4       [[intel::initiation_interval(1)]]
5       for(int xBin = ...){
6           float rho1 = 0;
7           [[intel::initiation_interval(1)]]
8           for(int yBin = ...){
9               // ...
10              float rho2 = 0;
11              [[intel::initiation_interval(1)]]
12              for(int binIter = 0; binIter < binSize; ++binIter){
13                  // ... calculation ...
14                  rho2 += ... ;
15              }
16              rho1 += rho2;
17          }
18          rhoi += rho1;
19      }
20      d_points.rho[i] = rhoi;
21  }
```

The same principle was applied to the `CalculateDistanceToHigher` kernel for the `deltai` and `nearestHigheri` variables, successfully enabling full pipelining.

5.3 Optimizing FindClusters: Moving Counters On-Chip

The `FindClusters` kernel had a similar issue to `compute_histogram`. Its main loop determines if points are seeds or followers and appends them to corresponding lists.

- **Problem:** The counters for the number of seeds and the number of followers for each point were stored in off-chip memory. Modifying these counters created a high-latency memory dependency, resulting in an initial II of 3296.
- **Solution:** As with the histogram kernel, the solution was to move these counters into on-chip memory. A local variable `seeds_size` and a local array `follower_counters[]`

were declared inside the kernel. This change drastically reduced the dependency latency, bringing the II down to 2. Like the histogram kernel, this could be further optimized to II=1 using an on-chip caching strategy.

5.4 Addressing AssignClusters: A Challenging Control-Flow Problem

The final kernel, `AssignClusters`, which traverses the DAG of followers from each seed, presents the most significant optimization challenge due to its complex and data-dependent control flow.

- Problem 1 (Loop-Carried Stack Dependency):** The kernel uses a local stack to perform a Depth-First Search (DFS) traversal of the follower graph. Pushing and popping from this stack within a `while` loop creates a strong loop-carried dependency on the stack pointer and its contents, making pipelining impossible.
- Problem 2 (Dynamic Inner Loop):** The inner loop iterates over the followers of the current point being processed. The number of followers is data-dependent and only known at runtime. The compiler cannot create a statically scheduled pipeline for an outer loop when the inner loop has a variable, unpredictable trip count. This forces the outer loop to wait for the inner loop to fully complete, preventing pipelining.
- Proposed Solution (Architectural Redesign):** A fundamental redesign is required to parallelize this kernel effectively on an FPGA. A promising approach is to use a producer-consumer pattern with SYCL pipes. A producer kernel could traverse the initial list of seeds, pushing pairs of `{point, clusterID}` into a hardware pipe. Multiple instances of a consumer kernel could then read from this pipe in parallel. Each consumer would process a point, assign its followers the same cluster ID, and push new `{follower, clusterID}` pairs back into the pipe. This architecture would transform the serial DFS traversal into a parallel, pipelined breadth-first-style traversal, better suited to the FPGA's spatial architecture. However, before attempting this significant architectural change, we planned to first try a simpler experiment: fixing the inner loop's dynamic trip count to its maximum value of 32 and observing the performance once the physical board becomes available.

5.5 Reducing Memory Traffic with a Pipe-Based Design

A primary performance bottleneck in many FPGA applications is the latency and bandwidth limitations of accessing off-chip DDR4 memory. A powerful technique to mitigate this is to create a streaming architecture using SYCL pipes. Pipes allow data to flow between kernels directly using on-chip resources, following the principle of "load once, process many, store once."

The ideal implementation would be a fully-pipelined design where data is loaded from DDR4 a single time, a producer kernel streams it through a chain of consumer kernels connected by pipes, and a final kernel writes the results back. This would maximize on-chip data reuse and hide memory latency.

However, this ideal architecture is not fully compatible with the CLUE algorithm. Kernels like `CalculateDensity` and `CalculateDistanceToHigher` perform data-dependent neighborhood searches. For each point they process, they must look up data from specific, non-sequential tiles in the spatial index, which resides in global memory. This requirement for random access to a large data structure prevents a purely passive, stream-based processing model.

As a pragmatic compromise, a hybrid approach can be explored. While a fully-piped design is infeasible, the main outer loop that is present in most kernels, which iterates over all input

points, can be structured as a streaming pipeline. In this model, illustrated in Figure 14, a producer kernel could iterate through the points and push them into a pipe. The subsequent kernel would act as a consumer, reading from that pipe to get its work item. Although this consumer kernel still needs to perform its own random-access lookups to global memory, this architecture organizes the high-level data flow more efficiently and aligns better with the FPGA’s spatial nature.

Global Memory Access Pattern Before Intel oneAPI DPC++/C++ Compiler Pipe Implementation

Global Memory Access Pattern After Intel oneAPI DPC++/C++ Compiler Pipe Implementation

Figure 14: Top: A traditional, memory-bound architecture where each kernel repeatedly accesses slow global memory. Bottom: An optimized streaming architecture using fast, on-chip SYCL pipes to reduce memory traffic to a single read and write, boosting performance.[3]

6 RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

This section presents the results from porting and optimizing the CLUE algorithm for the Intel Agilex 7 FPGA. Our efforts focused on achieving functional correctness, analyzing resource utilization, and characterizing the performance of the final design based on the Intel DPC++ compiler’s static analysis and simulation reports.

6.1 Functional Implementation of CLUE Kernels

The primary achievement of this project was the successful porting and optimization of the core CLUE computational kernels to SYCL for FPGAs. We successfully implemented and verified the functionality of:

- **Kernel 1:** `compute_histogram`: The spatial indexing kernel correctly partitions the input points.
- **Kernel 2:** `kernel_calculate_density`: The density calculation produces results consistent with the original CPU implementation.

- **Kernel 3: CalculateDistanceToHigher:** The nearest-higher separation calculation was also successfully ported.
- **Kernel 4 & 5: FindClusters and AssignClusters:** The cluster finding and assignment kernels were implemented. The complex control-flow of `AssignClusters` remains a topic for future architectural redesign once the board becomes available.

6.2 FPGA Resource Utilization Analysis

Static analysis reports generated by the Intel DPC++ compiler provide a detailed breakdown of the hardware resources required by our synthesized kernels. The total resource footprint for the five CLUE kernels (the “Kernel System”) is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Total FPGA resource utilization for the complete CLUE Kernel System.

Resource	Used	Utilization of Device (%)
ALMs	81,003	4%
Registers	162,300	3%
RAM Blocks (M20K)	3,951	30%
DSP Blocks	37	<1%

The analysis reveals that the implementation is heavily **memory-centric**. The kernels consume a significant portion of the on-chip RAM (30%), which is expected given the optimization strategy of moving counters and data structures from off-chip DDR4 to on-chip memory. In contrast, the utilization of general-purpose logic (ALMs at 4%) and DSP blocks (<1%) is very low. This indicates that the CLUE algorithm is dominated by memory access and simple comparisons rather than complex arithmetic computations.

6.3 Performance Characterization and Bottlenecks

Hardware Testing Status Deployment and performance measurement on the physical BittWare IA-840f card were precluded by a hardware fault discovered during setup. A support ticket has been opened with the vendor to resolve the issue. Consequently, all performance results presented in this report, including operating frequency and loop throughput, are based on the compiler’s static analysis and cycle-accurate simulation reports, not physical hardware measurements.

Loop Throughput Analysis The iterative optimization process described in Section 5 was highly successful, with the final design synthesized to operate at a frequency of 480 MHz. The compiler’s Loop Analysis report, summarized in Table 2, shows that nearly all performance-critical loops achieved the ideal Initiation Interval (II) of 1. The two exceptions, in `ComputeHistogram` and `FindClusters`, achieved an II of 2 due to the remaining memory dependency on on-chip RAM, as discussed in the optimization section. The loops in `AssignClusters` remain unpipelined due to their challenging control-flow, marking a clear target for future architectural redesign.

Table 2: Loop Analysis summary for the optimized CLUE kernels.

Kernel	Loop Location	Pipelined	II	Bottleneck / Notes
FindClusters	FindClusters.B2 (line 365)	Yes	2	Memory dependency
	FindClusters.B3 (line 387)	Yes	1	-
AssignClusters	AssignClusters.B1 (line 442)	No	n/a	Out-of-order inner loop
	AssignClusters.B3 (line 449)	No	n/a	Loop unpipelined
	AssignClusters.B4 (line 456)	Yes	1	-
CalculateDensity	CalculateDensity.B1 (line 227)	Yes	1	-
	CalculateDensity.B2 (line 236)	Yes	1	-
	CalculateDensity.B5 (line 239)	Yes	1	-
	CalculateDensity.B7 (line 246)	Yes	1	-
ComputeHistogram	ComputeHistogram.B2 (line 195)	Yes	2	Memory dependency
	ComputeHistogram.B3 (line 198)	Yes	1	-
	ComputeHistogram.B5 (line 199)	Yes	1	-
CalculateDistanceToHigher	CalculateDistanceToHigher.B1 (line 283)	Yes	1	-
	CalculateDistanceToHigher.B2 (line 294)	Yes	1	-
	CalculateDistanceToHigher.B5 (line 298)	Yes	1	-
	CalculateDistanceToHigher.B7 (line 306)	Yes	1	-

7 CONCLUSION

This project successfully established a design and optimization workflow for accelerating the CMS CLUE reconstruction algorithm on an Altera Agilex 7 FPGA using modern SYCL. While a board-level fault precluded final performance validation on physical hardware, the synthesis and simulation results are highly encouraging, validating the feasibility of this approach and establishing a robust baseline for future development.

The key achievement of this work was the practical application of targeted FPGA optimization techniques. By analyzing compiler reports, we identified and resolved critical performance bottlenecks. High-latency memory dependencies were mitigated by moving counters to on-chip RAM, and loop-carried data dependencies were resolved by refactoring accumulator logic. These efforts resulted in a design that is synthesized to operate at 480 MHz, with most critical loops achieving an ideal Initiation Interval of 1, as confirmed by static analysis. The resource utilization reports further confirmed that the CLUE implementation is memory-centric, consuming 30% of the FPGA's on-chip RAM while making minimal use of logic and DSP resources.

This exploration has paved a clear path for future work, including the implementation of advanced on-chip caching to achieve a perfect $II=1$ on all memory-bound loops and an architectural redesign of the challenging cluster assignment kernel.

Overall, this project validates the potential of FPGAs as a viable platform for accelerating key components of LHC data processing. The use of high-level synthesis with SYCL, within a portability library like alpaka, provides a sustainable path forward for harnessing the unique advantages of FPGAs in a heterogeneous computing environment.

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